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Representatives of different ethnic communities are characterized by ethnopsychological peculiarities (EPP), which determine the ethnocultural specificity of the system of relations of the speaker of linguistic culture to the surrounding reality and are manifested in speech behavior during the interaction of representatives of different cultures.

Due to the fact that the basis of the EPP of the speaker of a foreign language culture is the mentality, therefore, the EPP, like the mentality, is manifested in the intercultural communication in the perception, understanding and assessment of reality, national value orientations and behavioral strategies [5, p. 15]. A special set of assignments has been developed to form the sociocultural competence (SCC) of the linguistic university students taking into account the EPP of a speaker of a different culture. This complex implements the methodological principles of the interconnected communicative and sociocultural development of the student's

DEVELOPING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE: EXPLORING AND ASSESSING

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the indicative tasks for the formation of socio-cultural competence in the process of teaching students of language specialties to intercultural communication. The tasks are aimed at mastering students' knowledge of the ethnopsychological characteristics of the native speaker of the studied language and the ability to use this knowledge in the process of interaction.

personality, the phased formation of the SCC and the comparison of foreign and native cultures. Modern researchers define the assignments as a structural unit of the methodological organization of the material and recognize that the assignment is a reflection of the basic characteristics of the entire educational process. The structure of the assignment includes a communicative task and an indication of how to solve it, the language material to be implemented by the given methods, and the method of supposed control or self-control [1, p. 199].

The indicative component is presented in the statement of the assignment, which justifies the motive for the future speech action, directs the learner to the implementation of a specific communicative task and acts as a stimulus for the learner's speech actions. The executive component involves the direct implementation of the intended task. The controlling component of the task is aimed at exercising control or self-control, since

the assignment contains certain objective requirements for the result of the upcoming action, which the student can analyze, compare with the result obtained, comprehend and draw conclusions about the quality of the solution of the communicative task.

In accordance with the selected components, the assignment is carried out in several steps with the simultaneous activation of the linguistic, substantive, pragmatic and intercultural aspects: familiarizing with the intercultural situation, identifying and explaining the reasons for the misunderstanding between the participants in the situation, searching for language tools for expressing one or another communicative intention and their use in situations of ICC, the organization of interaction with a speaker of a foreign language culture.

Indicative tasks are of a speech-preparatory nature and involve the mastery of sociocultural knowledge and the development of skills to navigate the carrier of the language being studied and in terms of interaction. When developing indicative tasks, we proceed from the theory of the phased formation of mental actions P. Y. Galperin [2], according to which internal mental actions are the result of internalization of external objective actions. The process of understanding external objective actions involves mastering knowledge, as well as analyzing, comparing, evaluating, on the basis of which there is an understanding of external objective actions and planning of verbal interaction. In accordance with the theory of the phased formation of mental actions, we distinguished three types of indicative tasks: comparative, evaluative and planning.

Comparative assignments are aimed at identifying typical EPP; analysis and comparison of typical EPP; development of sociocultural observability, sociocultural impartiality and the cultivation of sociocultural susceptibility. Assignments for identifying typical EPP of native and target languages include:

- definition of national value orientations:
 - study the “value capsule” and extract information on the attitude of Americans toward ... from the “capsule”;
 - study the “value capsule” and supplement the statements;
 - study the “value capsule” and find answers to the questions posed;
 - study the situation and find confirmation of the indicated national value orientations: } Study the situation and find the facts that prove individualism and self-reliance of Americans. Explain the situation, using the Value Capsule “Individual freedom and self-reliance of Americans”. } Watch the video episode and identify the national value orientations of native speakers of American linguistic culture.
- determination of the norms of foreign language communicative behavior:
 - study the “language capsule” (watch an episode from the movie) and identify the language tools that Americans use for ...;
 - analyze the “language capsule” and supplement the statements with information from the “language capsule”;
 - study the “language capsule” and choose effective techniques for ...;
 - study the dialogue and find cues for expression ...
- determination of the sociocultural problem of inadequate speech behavior:
 - study dialogues, find and explain errors in the behavior of communicants: } Study the compliments and tell what is wrong with them. Explain the behavior of the communicators in the dialogues. Use the

Value Capsule “The power of positive thinking” and the Language Capsule “Making a compliment”. – study the situation and explain the problem that the participants encountered. Tasks for the analysis and comparison of typical EPP of native speakers of foreign and native cultures in situations of ICC include:

- comparison of the attitude of the speaker of the studied language to himself and to his personal space: – study the situation, compare and explain the behavior of the participants; } Determine whether the statements about the speakers of the language you are learning are true for speakers of the native culture: There are some statements from the Value Capsule “Friendliness versus friendship”. Define if they are true of the people of your country. Prove your opinion.

- Comparison of national value orientations: – Compare and explain the national value orientations of representatives of American and native cultures; – Answer questions about the national value orientations of Americans and give answers to the same questions about native cultural speakers: } Of the multiple-choice questions, choose one point about Americans and answer the same question about people of your country. Use the information in the Value Capsule “Attitude of Americans to work”.

- watch the episode and compare how national value orientations are manifested in the behavior of participants.

- comparison of the norms of foreign language communicative behavior: – study the situation and explain the behavior of representatives of foreign and native cultures: } Study the situation and explain the reasons for the behavior of the participants. How would you behave in such a situation? • comment on the statements about the norms of behavior of the carriers of the studied and native cultures: – Comment on the opinion of the American professors about the verbal behavior of Belarusian students studying in the USA. Express your attitude. Evaluation tasks involve the assessment by the student of the conditions for the interaction of the communicants (the purpose of the speech interaction, the characteristics of the communicative situation, the positions of the partners, the sequence of the communicative steps), predicting the interlocutor’s reaction in order to select an appropriate variant of speech behavior. Subtypes of assessment tasks are tasks for: assessment of the conditions of interaction; forecasting the reaction of a foreign language interlocutor. The presented complex provides for the mastery of sociocultural knowledge of the EPP of the native speaker of the studied language, the development of sociocultural skills and sociocultural abilities, as well as the upbringing of sociocultural qualities, increasing the success of teaching intercultural communication in a linguistic university.

References:

1. Bim, I. L. Methods of teaching foreign languages as a science and problems of a school textbook. M. : Russian language, 1977. 240 p.
2. Galperin, P. Y. Introduction to Psychology: Textbook. M., 1999. 332 p.

3. Kitaygorodskaya, G. A. Intensive teaching of foreign languages: theory and practice. M., 1992. 254 p. 4. Leontiev, A. A. Psychology of communication. Tartu, 1974. 218 p. 5. Pochinok, T. V.